

Investigation of Structural and Optoelectronic Properties of N-Doped Hexagonal Phases of TiO₂ (TiO_{2-x}N_x) Nanoparticles with DFT Realization: OPTIMIZATION of the Band Gap and Optical Properties for Visible-Light Absorption and Photovoltaic Applications

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Abstract: The geometric structure, electronic and optical properties of N-doped TiO₂ (TiO_{2-x}N_x) were studied within the framework of density functional theory. The effective electron-electron exchange-correlation functional and the modified Becke–Johnson potential were used to calculate electronic and optical properties. The calculated optical parameters and the density of electronic states indicate that the TiO_{2-x}N_x (0.06 ≤ x ≤ 0.25) system has a property favorable for application in solar cells. The calculated structural characteristics show that the size of these systems increases with the increasing concentration of additives. The electronic properties of N-doped TiO₂ show that the bandgaps tend to decrease, and some 2p states of N atoms are located inside the bandgap, which leads to a decrease in the photon energy of the transition and absorption of visible light. As a result, the bandgap effectively decreases with doping concentration increase, while the absorption is effectively improved due to the extended absorption range, both ultraviolet, visible, and infrared range of light emission. It was found that the optimal concentration of nitrogen doping (12.5 at.%) noticeably increases the absorption capacity; hence, the conversion efficiency of TiO₂ in the visible region of radiation and effectively reduces the bandgap from 3.2 to 2.4 eV. However, any further increase in concentration does not lead to an additional improvement of the absorption capacity despite the change in the bandgap, which is in good agreement with the existing experimental data. These superior characteristics make N-doped TiO₂ a promising material for low-cost, high-efficiency solar cells for the mass market.

Keywords: titanium dioxide; doping, electronic properties; bandgap; quantum mechanical calculations; optical properties; visible region.

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1. Introduction

Molecular modeling with different computational methods shows a potential application for elucidating physical, chemical, and biological properties for several systems and molecules [1-5]. Among other computational methods, density functional theory DFT is widely used as an effective tool for elucidating structural, magnetic, elastic and optoelectronic properties for a wide range of systems [6-9].

On the other hand, solar power is the most promising renewable energy source, and low-cost photovoltaic technologies are making progress in the market. Research on dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) usually based on nanocrystalline TiO₂ has been extensively pursued, and the number of papers and patents published in this area has grown exponentially over the last ten years. Research efforts have largely focused on optimizing the dye, but recently the TiO₂ nanocrystalline electrode itself has attracted more attention. It has been shown that particle size and shape, crystallinity, surface morphology, optoelectronic properties and chemistry of the TiO₂ material are key parameters to be controlled for optimized performance of the solar cell. However, pure TiO₂ has three drawbacks that limit its practical application. First, the bandgap of pure undoped TiO₂, depending on its crystalline phase, is in the range of 3-3.2 eV, which is almost inactive when irradiated with visible light. Therefore, stable solar energy of AM 1.5 spectra cannot be converted, and it exhibits significant activity only when irradiated with ultraviolet light of less than 360 nm.

In this regard, many efforts have been directed to overcome the disadvantages and optimize the absorption capacity and photocatalytic properties of TiO₂, especially in the visible light range. Chemical modifications of TiO₂ are one of the possible ways to improve material photoactivity. This can be carried out by the addition of metal ions, non-metallic atoms to TiO₂ crystal lattice, or sensitization of TiO₂ with dyes. Among them, ionic and cationic doping with the formation of structural defects is an effective approach [10]. The possibility of using this approach is precisely due to the fact that the energy levels of such defects can be located in the band so that the absorption of light by defects (impurity absorption) is also possible in the longer wavelength region [11]. The efficiency of such an approach was shown in many works, but the activity depends on many parameters, such as the concentration of the dopant, the energy levels of the dopant in the titanium dioxide lattice, and the distribution of doping atoms [12]. According to [13], metal ions in the titanium oxide matrix significantly affect the absorption spectrum, charge carriers' recombination rate, and mobility. Doping ions with a stable configuration, such as Fe³⁺, Gd³⁺, Ru³⁺, and Os³⁺, lead to a narrowing of the bandgap or the appearance of additional energy levels (bathochromic effect), which improve the charge transfer to the conduction band and facilitate the absorption of visible light, due to the improvement of optoelectronic properties.

For TiO₂ doped with non-metallic elements in the anionic positions, in most cases, an increase in the absorption capacity in the visible spectra is observed, while the photoactivity decreases under UV irradiation. It is known that C, S, F and N - doped titanium dioxide exhibit significantly higher photoactivity compared to pure TiO₂, and among them, nitrogen is the best candidate for optimizing TiO₂ with visible light [14].

On the other hand, the inclusion (alloying) of nitrogen into the TiO₂ lattices, in contrast to the addition of other impurities, is carried out by most known physical and chemical methods, such as ball mill, chemical vapor deposition, direct low-temperature nitridation method, deposition of atomic layers, sputtering, plasma or ion implantation, sol-gel method,

solvothermal method, hydrothermal method, direct hydrolysis of organic/inorganic salts and oxidation of titanium nitride or pernitride (nitrogen source commonly used for TiO₂ synthesis). The most widespread and effective method is the direct synthesis of titanium pernitride (TiN₂) from TiO₂ in the nitrogen atmosphere [15].

A sufficient amount of work has been devoted to doping with a nitrogen of the anatase TiO₂ cell, which showed that doping shifts the absorption edge to the region of lower energies and increases the absorption capacity of the material in the visible region by reducing the bandgap [14, 16-19]. Moreover, it was found that nitrogen doping in oxygen position is very optimal due to the comparable atomic size, low ionization energy, and stability. Titanium dioxide doped in oxygen position has both shallow donor and acceptor levels above the conduction and valence bands, respectively, due to the oxygen vacancy [17] and TiO₂ (in the structure of anatase and rutile) containing nitrogen in the interstices of the crystal lattice has isolated impurity levels in the bandgap.

Despite extensive research devoted to this problem in recent years, the effect of doping with nitrogen in the hexagonal lattice of TiO₂ has not yet been fully studied. In the present article, by means of *ab initio* calculations, the structural electronic and optical characteristics of the N-doped hexagonal TiO₂ phase were predicted.

2. Materials and Methods

The geometric structure of the hexagonal TiO_{2-x}N_x ($0.06 \leq x \leq 0.25$) was investigated within the framework of DFT using the augmented wave package of the plane-wave basis projector WIEN2k [20]. Geometry optimization was carried out by relaxing all atomic positions in the cell and the cell shape. The determination of structural specification is unavoidable for the description of the structural behavior of materials. The structural parameters, i.e., lattice constant (a_0), bulk modulus (B), and the pressure derivative of the bulk modulus (B'), are determined. The total energy (in Ryd or eV) of the unit cell for every compound was calculated by fluctuating the unit cell volume and plotted against the correlative energies for optimization. Murnaghan's equation of state was used to calculate bulk Modulii and the lattice constants. Murnaghan's equation of state assumes that the bulk modulus varies inversely with pressure [21]. The mathematical form of Murnaghan's equation of state is given by

$$P(v) = \frac{B}{B'} \left[\left(\frac{V_0}{v} \right)^{B'} - 1 \right] \quad (1)$$

$$(v) = \frac{B}{B'} \left[\left(\frac{a_0}{a} \right)^{3B'} - 1 \right] \quad (2)$$

where $P(v)$ is the pressure, B is the bulk modulus, B' is the pressure derivative of bulk modulus, V_0 and a_0 are the equilibrium volume and lattice constant, i.e., when the system is in relax state.

Electron-electron correlation was expressed by the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) proposed by Perdew, Becke, and Ernzerhof (GGA-PBE) [22]. A $2 \times 2 \times 1$ k-point mesh was selected in the Brillouin zone according to Monkhorst-Pack (MP) scheme [23]. The plane-wave cutoff was chosen to be 400 eV.

Electronic structure calculations within the DFT after geometry optimization were performed using the full-potential augmented plane wave and local orbit, used to study the complex properties of solids, the WIEN2k package [24], where the modified Becke-Johnson

(mBJ) potential refined by Tran and Blaha (TB-mBJ) [25] was employed for the electron-electron correlation functional. DFT is a quantum approach based on the first principle calculations proposed by Hohenberg, Kohn, and Sham [26, 27]. The method has the advantage of not relying on any experimental parameters. The idea of the method is to replace the interacting electronic system with a fictitious non-interacting electronic system, which gives the same electron density as the interacting system. The Kohn - Sham equation [26] is based on two theorems of Hohenberg and Kohn [27] for calculating the Hamiltonian (total energy) of a many-electron system, which begins with writing the Schrödinger equation in the form:

$$\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 + E_{ion}(r) + E_h(r) + E_{xc}(r) \right) \psi_i(r) = E \psi_i(r) \quad (3)$$

Here, $E_{ion}(r)$ is the ionic potential (the sum of the potentials of the electron-electron, electron-proton (nuclear), and proton-proton interaction), $E_h(r)$ is the Hartree potential, and $E_{xc}(r)$ is the exchange-correlation potential. The last 2 potentials are calculated as:

$$E_h(r) = e^2 \int \frac{\rho(r')}{|r-r'|} dr' \quad (4)$$

$$E_{xc}(r) = \frac{\delta \epsilon_{xc}[\rho(r)]}{\delta \rho(r)} \quad (5)$$

where $\rho(r)$ is the electron density functional.

Hohenberg and Kohn showed in 1964 within the framework of the DFT that the electron density functional $\rho(r)$ for the normalized ψ is defined as

$$\rho(r) = N \int d^3r_2 \dots \int d^3r_N \psi^*(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_2, \dots, \vec{r}_N) \psi(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_2, \dots, \vec{r}_N) \quad (6)$$

For the density of the ground state $\rho_0(r)$, it is possible in principle to calculate the corresponding wave function of the ground state $\psi_0(r_1, \dots, r_N)$, where N is the number of electrons. In other words, ψ is a unique functional of $\rho_0(r)$.

$$\psi_0 = \psi(\rho_0) \quad (7)$$

Thus, the density functional is defined as:

$$\rho(r) = \sum_{\text{states } i} \psi_i^*(r) \psi_i(r) \quad (8)$$

Within the DFT-Wien2k, for the corresponding $\rho(r)$, E_h and E_{xc} are first calculated, and then the solution of the Schrödinger equation (equation 3) is performed. Then, from the eigenstates ($\psi_i(r)$), the electron density functional ($\rho(r)$) is calculated using Equation 8.

The electron exchange-correlation potential (E_{xc}) for a non-interactive electron system can be obtained from the energy in which only the electron density functions. It has been shown in many works that the Becke and Johnson exchange-correlation potential (mBJ) gives an accurate and experimentally comparable estimate of the bandgap [28-33] in comparison with known approximations, such as the GGA. The Becke and Johnson potential is determined by the following equation:

$$E_{xc}^{mBJ}(r) = cE_x^{BR}(r) + (3c - 2) \frac{1}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{5k(r)}{6\rho(r)}} \quad (9),$$

where $k(r)$ is the kinetic energy density according to the Kohn-Sham equation, $\rho(r)$ is the electron density and E_x^{BR} - is the Becke-Roussel exchange functional (BR). Although this potential cannot be used to calculate the forces acting on nuclei, as required for geometry

optimization, the only function of mBJ is to overcome the underestimation of the band gap and obtain a value consistent with the experimental results.

When calculating electronic and optical properties, muffin-tin radii for Ti, O and N were set equal to 1,87 a.u., 1,69 a.u., and N – 1,72 a.u. The plane wave cutoff K_{max} , was chosen to be $3.0 \text{ Ry}^{1/2}$. The k-point mesh was $3 \times 2 \times 3$ for all calculations using the MP scheme.

3. Results and Discussion

The structural parameters of $\text{TiO}_{2-x}\text{N}_x$ ($0.06 \leq x \leq 0.25$) optimized within the GGA are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. The value of the structural parameters of the hexagonal system $\text{TiO}_{2-x}\text{N}_x$ ($0.06 \leq x \leq 0.25$).

System ($\text{TiO}_{2-x}\text{N}_x$)	Lattice parameters, Å			System volume, Å ³
	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	
TiO ₂	5.8871	5.8871	8.9066	267.3350
TiO _{1.96} N _{0.06}	5.9022	5.9279	8.9989	272.5836
TiO _{1.88} N _{0.12}	5.9453	5.9309	9.0905	277.8219
TiO _{1.82} N _{0.18}	5.9472	5.9395	9.7719	299.0431
TiO _{1.75} N _{0.25}	5.9613	5.9372	9.8501	302.3236

Since the ionic radius of the N ion is greater than that of the O ion, the calculated cell volume, as shown in Table 1, increases quasi-linearly with increasing N concentration, which suggests that the volume change obeys Vegard's law.

We investigated the electronic properties of the $\text{TiO}_{2-x}\text{N}_x$ system in the form of the dependence of the energy of the forbidden zone on the density of electronic states (DOS) in the unit cell. Therefore, understanding their formation becomes vital for developing and manufacturing optoelectronic, magneto-optical, and magnetoelectronic devices. The calculated total density of electronic states of the structurally optimized models of $\text{TiO}_{2-x}\text{N}_x$ described above is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Total density of electronic states (TDOS) for $\text{TiO}_{2-x}\text{N}_x$.

A decrease in the density of electronic states for N - doped systems compared with pure TiO_2 means a decrease in vacancies in their outer electron orbitals. For undoped TiO_2 , a high degree of density of states is observed compared to other members of this system. Calculations

of the electronic properties of N-doped TiO₂ show that with an increase in the nitrogen concentration, the bandgap tends to decrease; however, at a certain critical percentage ($x = 0.25$), the energy of the bandgap begins to increase. Some 2p states of N atoms lie inside the bandgap. These shallow (deep) states inside the bandgap lead to a decrease in the photon energy of the transition and absorption of visible light.

The calculated band gaps of these materials are summarized in Table 2. Since the GGA approximation mainly underestimates the band gap, we used the TB–mBJ potential for the electron–electron exchange–correlation functional in the current electronic structure calculations.

Table 2. Results of calculations of the bandgap for TiO_{2-x}N_x ($0.06 \leq x \leq 0.25$) system.

System (TiO _{2-x} N _x)	Bandgap, eV
TiO ₂	3.228
TiO _{1.96} N _{0.06}	2.253
TiO _{1.88} N _{0.12}	2.171
TiO _{1.82} N _{0.18}	2.068
TiO _{1.75} N _{0.25}	2.417

Reduction of the bandgap is critical for TiO_{2-x}N_x applications, especially for photovoltaic applications. The calculated band gaps are plotted in Figure 2, suggesting that the band gap decreases with increasing N concentration x in TiO_{2-x}N_x ($0.06 \leq x \leq 0.25$).

Figure 2. Calculated values of the bandgap versus nitrogen concentration.

The least-squares fitting to the calculated bandgap shown by the solid line in Figure 2, is expressed by the following formula: $E_{BG} = 48,235x^2 - 14,888x + 3,1546$, from which one can estimate the band gap value in TiO_{2-x}N_x for any N concentration, i.e., $0.06 \leq x \leq 0.25$. In other words, it can be said that by controlling the N content, the bandgap can be adjusted to approach the optimal bandgap.

According to Figure 2, the bandgap of TiO_{2-x}N_x decreases with increasing nitrogen concentration, first due to an increase in the radius of substitute ions (N), and then sharply increases. In this case, it was found that the optimal percentage of doping with nitrogen (12.5 at.% N) effectively reduces the bandgap of TiO₂ from 3.2 to 2.4 eV. However, any further

increase in concentration despite a change in the bandgap does not have any additional improvement in the material's absorbency. A similar pattern was reported in [34], in which the authors reported that the optimal doping of nitrogen for anatase structure is 1.2 wt%, and higher or lower concentration of nitrogen doping leads to ineffective absorption of visible light, as well as to increase of charge carriers recombination rate.

Then the optical properties were calculated using the optic code implemented in the WIEN2k package. Figures 3(a) and 3(b) show the real and imaginary parts of the dielectric constants, ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 , respectively, for an entire family of the systems under study.

Figure 3. (a, b). Real (a) and imaginary parts (b) of the dielectric constant of nanocrystals of the $\text{TiO}_{2-x}\text{N}_x$ system.

Figure 3a shows that materials exhibit a metallic behavior at sufficiently high incident photon energies. A negative value of ϵ_1 indicates that the system has a metallic nature. That is, it is possible to investigate and evaluate the metallicity of the compound by its real function. In this case, the optical bandgap has feedback between them. On the other hand, the imaginary part, ϵ_2 , represents the absorption capacity; the behavior of the ϵ_2 function for materials should exhibit an increase in energy, which is suitable for photovoltaic applications. Basically, this gives information about how the material reacts when the disturbance is caused by electromagnetic radiation and directly depends on its band structure. The ϵ_2 value indicates that these materials can absorb the maximum amount of energy in a wide range of photon energies and, coincidentally, can hold this energy.

The calculated absorption coefficients, α , taking into account $\alpha = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \sqrt{\epsilon_2} = \frac{2\omega\sqrt{\epsilon_2}}{c}$, are shown in Figure 4 for all investigated materials.

According to Figure 4, N doped TiO_2 exhibits higher activity in both UV and visible light than undoped TiO_2 due to improved light response in the range from 360 to 720 nm, narrowing the bandgap. Also, titanium dioxide doped with 12.5 at.%, Activity is observed under IR irradiation of light. All samples show an absorption edge between 540 and 720 nm due to the excitation of electrons from the valence band to the conduction band of the TiO_2 base material. With an increase in the N content in TiO_2 , not only the absorptive capacity is observed but also the redshift of the absorption edge in the infrared region. This optical absorption shows a strong interaction between TiO_2 and N atoms, which leads to an increase in the surface electric charge of TiO_2 at the expense of the N atoms. It is also beneficial for the ease of charge transfer between TiO_2 and N. It therefore leads to an increase in the ability of

TiO₂ to absorb light in the visible area, which is an excellent aspect for the light-harvesting capacity of solar panels.

Figure 4. Graphs of the dependence of the absorption coefficient (optical absorption spectra) on the wavelength for the TiO_{2-x}N_x system.

Finally, to find out the effect of different nitrogen contents on the optical properties of TiO₂, the optical band gap of all TiO_{2-x}N_x systems was calculated. The representative optical energy width was calculated using the Kubelka - Munk functions $(\alpha hv)^{1/2}$ (where α is the absorption coefficient) as a function of the photon energy (hv). The calculated optical bandgap, according to the plot of $(\alpha hv)^{1/2}$ versus energy, is lower than that of pure TiO₂, which is associated with nitrogen doping by mixing the N (2p) and O (2p) states of nitrogen and TiO₂ (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Plot of $(\alpha hv)^{1/2}$ versus photon energy to analyze the optical energy of the bandgap.

The bandgap of the optical energy was determined by plotting the intersection tangent to the x-axis (Figure 5). As can be seen, it's decreasing from 3.3 to 1.15 eV with increasing nitrogen content in TiO₂. Unlike pure titanium dioxide, the optical band gap for nitrogen-doped titanium dioxide nanocrystals, that is, the system TiO_{1.96}N_{0.06}, TiO_{1.88}N_{0.12}, TiO_{1.82}N_{0.18}, and TiO_{1.75}N_{0.25} are 3.05eV, 2.42 eV, 1.85 eV, and 1.15 eV, respectively, which convincing

evidence of absorption of visible and IR light compared to undoped TiO₂. Optical studies have shown that doping with nitrogen ions leads to an increase in the absorption edge wavelength and a decrease in the energy of the bandgap of TiO₂ nanoparticles.

The origin of the mechanism of absorption and photoexcitation of visible light over TiO₂ doped with nitrogen is based on electron-hole pairs when irradiated with photon energies exceeding the bandgap. The generation of electrons in the conduction band and holes in the valence band upon irradiation with visible light is impossible for an undoped system because of the wide bandgap of pure TiO₂ (Figure 6 (a)). The process of incorporating nitrogen into the TiO₂ lattice leads to the formation of a new average energy state, i.e., 2p orbitals of N atoms above the O (2p) valence band, which ultimately decreases the bandgap of TiO₂ (for example, for 12.5 at.% N it decreases to ~ 2.4 eV) and shifts the optical absorption to the visible light region (Figure 6 (b)). The proposed schematic diagram (Figure 6 (a, b)) represents the state with a reduced bandgap after doping with nitrogen and the possibility of electron transition from the valence band to the conduction band.

Figure 6. (a, b). Energy level diagrams of pure and N - doped TiO₂.

The results obtained can contribute to understanding some of the features of their optical properties, which are important for the practical application of the systems under study. They may be of interest to researchers looking for materials with specified optical characteristics. The first-principles results were obtained to satisfy the criteria for making N-doped TiO₂ a feasible material in a dye-sensitized solar cell. Although the absorption edge shifts toward higher energies as the N concentration increases, as expected due to the change in the bandgap, all of these materials seem to be suitable for photovoltaic applications.

The obtained data revealed that DFT computational data is one of concern for studying electronic properties of molecular systems as well as the structural and optoelectronic properties of N-doped hexagonal TiO₂. These findings are in good agreement with those obtained previously [35-52].

4. Conclusions

In the present work, the structural, electronic, and optical properties for a number of nanocrystals from the TiO_{2-x}N_x family were investigated by implementing quantum-chemical calculations. Calculations showed that the bandgap decreases with an increase of the nitrogen concentration, and doping concentration of 12.5 at.% is optimal. According to our calculations, the value of the bandgap for TiO₂, TiO_{1.96}N_{0.06}, TiO_{1.88}N_{0.12}, TiO_{1.82}N_{0.18} and TiO_{1.75}N_{0.25} nanocrystals are 3.228 eV, 2.253 eV, 2.171 eV, 2.068 eV, and 2.417 eV, respectively. The calculated optical properties, consisting of the imaginary and real parts of the dielectric function and the absorption coefficients, have shown that titanium dioxide doping increases the

absorption coefficient compared to pure TiO₂. High absorption power and wideband forward bandgaps predict that these materials are suitable for solar cell applications.

Other researchers can use obtained results to model the structure of substances expected to be synthesized and determine such an important component as "composition-structure-property".

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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